

CALCULATION OF PARAMETERS AFFECTING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE SPRINKLER IRRIGATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. In this article, the parameters affecting the effectiveness of the sprinkler irrigation system are considered based on research. Losses due to wind flow and evaporation were taken into account as the main parameters in these parameters. Several researches were studied, formulas developed based on the analysis were applied to the obtained research results, and change graphs were made. In addition, the discharge and throw radius from the sprinkler irrigation system in the pressure change were analyzed based on the field conditions and the results given by the manufacturer, and the losses were calculated using them. Also, the calculation of the necessary parameters in the implementation of the hydraulic calculation of the sprinkler irrigation system and the evaluation of its efficiency is given based on the analysis of various literature.

Key words. Sprinkler effectiveness, hydraulic calculation, wind drift, evaporation losses.

1 INTRODUCTION

The sprinkler irrigation method is one of the most effective and widely used irrigation methods around the world. This method is mainly used for watering vegetables and valuable crops. The sprinkler irrigation method can save water by 10-35% and increase crop yield by 10-30%. Parameters such as uniform distribution of moisture, wind flow, evaporation are important in the operation of the sprinkler irrigation system. Martínez-cop (2008) and others explained WDEL (Wind draft and Evaporation Losses) by considering the trajectory of the amount of water coming out of the sprinkler nozzles across the crop area. Although some of these losses were due to wind flow, it was estimated that most of them corresponded to evaporation. Sanchez et al. (2011) noted that wind speed is one of the important parameters in calculating WDEL. According to Suryanarayana et al. (2013), as the area between the sprinklers increases, the uniformity of moisture distribution decreases horizontally, because the auxiliary nozzle in the sprinkler delivers less water than the main nozzle.

The sprinkler irrigation method is distinguished among pressurized irrigation methods as an irrigation method that requires low operating pressure and low labor force and high-water use efficiency (Koech and Langat, 2018). Sprinkler irrigation was adapted with different irrigation levels and samples were studied using Black gram equations for soil moisture distribution (Kumar et al., 2018). Silva et al. (2013) conducted an experiment with micro sprinkler irrigation method on different seeds of banana fruit and studied the soil wetting and distribution of the water coming out of the nozzle.

Wind speed, direction and evaporation were considered to be the main causes of water wastage and uneven distribution of moisture in sprinkler irrigation (Irmak et al., 2011). Uniform distribution of moisture in the soil depends on the types of sprinkler nozzles, their size, number, operating pressure and wind force. (Sistanto, 2014) calculated the coefficient of homogeneity and homogeneity of distribution. Operating pressure is one of the necessary parameters for achieving maximum water use efficiency and uniform distribution of moisture in the soil in the sprinkler irrigation system (Abd El-Wahed et al., 2016). The choice of sprinkler discharge is carried out in 2 different ways. The first method should not be less than the rate of soil infiltration. James and others point out that this is the most widely used method of cost estimation.

A number of problems arise as a result of improper hydraulic calculations in various water-saving irrigation technologies being designed today. These problems arise due to the fact that the system is not fully studied and there are many complex processes of the system and the existing literature is not used correctly. As a solution to such problems, in this article, hydraulic calculations of the sprinkler irrigation method and some parameters that affect it are taken into account, and after analyzing the conducted research, hydraulic calculations are developed, adapted to the conditions in Uzbekistan. In this, taking into account the violation of the distribution of water consumption due to wind and evapotranspiration, the distribution of moisture in the soil, the amount of water supplied to the crop area and the efficiency of the system according to the type of crop and the mechanical composition of the soil, the calculation of irrigation cycles, rates and similar important parameters is presented. The research work was carried out on the example of the results of the work on the sprinkler irrigation system installed in the conditions of Uzbekistan.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS.

To calculate WDEL, the depth of the water coming out of the sprinkler is calculated by ID_D (the sprinkler is determined according to the discharge, distance and irrigation time), the amount of water collected in the pluviometers is calculated by ID_c (Dechmi et al. 2003, Sanchez et al. 2011):

$$WDEL = (ID_D - ID_c/ID_D) * 100 \quad (1)$$

WDEL-downwind and evaporation losses

IDD-Water level coming out of sprinkler, mm

IDc-The amount of water collected in the pluviometer, mm

IDD-The water level in the sprinkler can be calculated as follows:

$$ID_D = (Q * t) / S \quad (2)$$

Q-sprinkler discharge;

t-watering time;
S-sprinkler spacing;
Sprinkler discharge is calculated as follows:

$$Q = \mu \omega \sqrt{2gH} \quad (3)$$

μ - discharge coefficient;
 ω -nozzle surface;
g-free fall acceleration;
H-head

The distribution of moisture in the soil is measured in the root zone. In this case, depending on the type of crop, the average distance is 90-120 cm. To calculate the distribution of moisture in the soil, the required volume of water and the volume of voids are needed:

Fig.1. Calculating volumetric water content

The ability to retain water falling on the soil, d , is determined by the following formula:

$$d = \frac{(TK - SN)}{100} \cdot \gamma_t \cdot D \quad (4)$$

here, d -soil water retention capacity, mm/m;
TK Boundary field wet capacity of -area,%;
SN-extinction point, %;
 γ_t -soil weight, g/cm³;
D-plant root depth, mm;

Field water capacity TK is the marginal field wet capacity, usually equal to 31.20%. The wilting point is SN, and if the soil is depleted of this water, the plant begins to wilt, equal to 14.18%. To calculate the soil weight γ_t , a sample is taken from the crop area and its weight is measured, then the soil is dried in a thermostat at 1050 for 5-6 hours and its mass is measured. Then it is dried again and its mass is measured. If there was no change in mass, the soil will be absolutely dry and this mass will be taken. Plant root depth D varies according to crop types:

For cotton, tomato, sunflower, corn - 90 cm
For potatoes, eggplants, cucumbers, beans, peppers - 60 cm

The rate of infiltration of the soil is important in the distribution of the amount of water coming out of the sprinkler over the crop area.

To determine the rate of infiltration, at least 2 samples are taken from every 2 hectares of the cultivated area and sent to the infiltration detection laboratory. In addition, values of infiltration according to the mechanical composition of the soil are given in various sources:

- □ Sandy soil: 25-250mm/h→50
- □ Light wind: 13-76mm/h→25
- □ Average rainfall: 8-20mm/h→13
- □ Heavy rain: 2.5-15mm/h→8
- □ Clay soil: 0.3-5mm/h→2.5

Based on the above values, the sprinkler spacing is S_d :

$$S_d = 0.9 * \sqrt{\frac{Q}{I}} \quad (5)$$

Here, Q-sprinkler discharge, I-infiltration rate.

In addition, according to the amount of precipitation in the area, the area coefficient P is determined depending on the required amount of water. For this, the amount of precipitation in the area is needed:

Table 1. The list of area coefficient's amount

#	Amount of precipitation, mm	P
1	0<360	0.35
2	360<750	0.3
3	750<	0.25

The value of the field coefficient is calculated in the following formula, and the amount of P is approximated based on the table:

$$P=k*S_d/S_s \quad (6)$$

Here, k is the crop root coefficient, the value of which is equal to 1; Spacing of ss-sprinklers.

Using these values, the amount of water required for each irrigation d_{nmax} is calculated by the following formula:

$$d_{nmax}=d_k*D*R_y*P \quad (7)$$

Here, d_k -(4) is calculated by d in the formula. In this case, D is calculated according to the depth of the root:

$$d_k=d_n/D \quad (8)$$

R_y -moisture that should be minimum in the soil. The maximum is equal to 0.3. That is, there should be at least 70% moisture in the soil.

The following formula is used to calculate the watering interval T:

$$T=ET*P_s/85 \quad (9)$$

T-watering interval, mm/day

ET is evapotranspiration, the value of which is readily obtained:

Cotton-11.4mm
Tomato-10mm
Cucumber-9mm
Pepper-9.5mm

Ps-coefficient, depending on the type of crop, the following values are obtained:

Cotton-80
Vegetables-80
Grape-75
Tree-70

The watering time is calculated as follows:

$$S_A = d_{nmax}/T \quad (10)$$

Amount of net irrigation water requirement to be used for each irrigation:

$$d_n = S_A * T \quad (11)$$

Gross amount of water per irrigation:

$$d_t = d_n / E_a \quad (12)$$

Here, E_a -system efficiency:

$E_a = 70\% = 0.70$ for sprinkler irrigation system

Number of sprinklers per hectare:

$$N_d = 10000 / (S_d * S_s) \quad (13)$$

Watering time calculation:

$$T_a = (10000 * d_t) / (q * N_d) \quad (14)$$

Number of irrigations:

$$N_{max} = T_g / T_a * S_A \quad (15)$$

T_g -pump operating time.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The amount of water coming out of the sprinkler was measured by conducting research in the sprinkler irrigation system installed in the conditions of Uzbekistan (Table 2). In this case, according to the change in effort, the value of consumption changes. In the table, the amount of water coming out of 3 different nozzles is measured separately and their average value is also given.

According to the above results, WDEL is calculated according to the formula (1).:

$$WDEL = (ID_D - ID_c / ID_D) * 100$$

Each term was calculated and the following results were obtained (table). The following link was created to calculate the ID_D of the water level coming out of the sprinkler:

$$ID_D = Q / (t * \omega)$$

Here, the average water level coming out of the Q-sprinkler discharge, m^3/h ;

t-time, h;

ω -sprinkler sprinkler surface, where the throw radius is used, m^2 ;

In addition to the results obtained from the research, the sprinkler catalog provided by the manufacturer for the type of sprinkler used, with the change in pressure, sprinkler discharge and throw radius are listed (Table 3). The calculations in this table are used to fill in Table 4.

Table 2. The difference between pressure and water consumption

Nozzle diameter	10 m		12 m		14 m		16 m		18 m		20 m	
	Discharge	Throwing radius										
r, mm	m ³ /h	m										
8	1.26	6	1.4	6.4	1.5	7	1.62	7.5	1.73	8	1.84	8.5
6	0.7	5.4	0.8	5.9	0.86	6.4	0.93	7	1.01	7.4	1.08	8
5	0.5	5	0.6	5.4	0.6	5.9	0.65	6.4	0.72	7	0.76	7.4

Table 3. The amount of water that should come out of the sprinkler and the radius of the shot.

Nozzle diameter	10 m		12 m		14 m		16 m		18 m		20 m	
	Discharge	Throwing radius										
r, mm	m ³ /h	m										
8	1.35	6	1.45	6.5	1.5	7	1.62	7.5	1.73	8	1.84	8.5
6	0.8	5.5	0.9	6	0.92	6.5	0.97	7	1.01	7.5	1.08	8
5	0.7	5	0.75	5.5	0.8	6	0.85	6.5	0.9	7	0.95	7.5

Table 4. Average discharge and throw radius of the sprinkler measured in the field and given by the company.

#	Sprinkler metered discharge, m ³ /h	Sprinkler measured throw radius, m	Discharge provided by the sprinkler, m ³ /h	Throwing radius given by the sprinkler, m
1	0.8	5.47	0.95	5.5
2	0.93	5.9	1.03	6
3	0.99	6.43	4.07	6.5
4	1.06	6.96	1.15	7
5	1.15	7.46	1.21	7.5
6	1.23	7.96	1.3	8

Table 5. WDEL calculation table

#	The water level coming out of the sprinkler, ID _D , mm	The water level in the measured containers, ID _C , mm	Loss due to wind and evaporation, WDEL, %	Head change, H, m
1	0.01000	0.00912	14.86	10
2	0.00911	0.00851	6.62	12
3	0.00807	0.00763	5.45	14
4	0.00747	0.00697	6.76	16
5	0.00685	0.00658	3.93	18
6	0.00647	0.00618	4.43	20

Fig 2. Sprinkler water level differences in 2 types of discharge

The amount of WDEL in head change

Fig 3. The amount of WDEL and Head changes throwing irrigation system

According to the above results, it was found that the spread of the discharge and the radius of the sprinkler depends on the pressure. Also, according to the above calculations used to calculate WDEL, the average loss was 5-10%.

At the next stage, taking into account the amount of water consumed by the WDEL, the calculation of parameters necessary for effective use of available water is calculated on the basis of the above formulas (4-15) and included in the hydraulic account in the design work.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In the article, several results were obtained on the basis of the parameters affecting the effectiveness of the sprinkler irrigation system. In this case, the amount of water coming out of the sprinkler and reaching the soil and through it to the crop is reduced by an average of 5-10% due to losses due to wind flow and evaporation. Also, the change in effort was taken into account in these losses. In addition, the connections that should be made in the design work and hydraulic calculations of the system were studied from various foreign literature and recommended based on experience. These recommendations consist of hydraulic calculations based on sprinkler spacing, soil water holding capacity, and rooting depth based on crop demand.

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